

ISic3009

Dedication to Damater(?)

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

statue base (?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2018.03.13 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in foundation works for post office, between via Eumelo, via Archia, and via Carabelli

Coordinates

37.070881, 15.284686

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica della Neapolis, Orecchio di Dionisio e Teatro Greco

Physical Description

Large block of grey limestone, broken to the right and the rear; the upper and lower face are finished smooth; the left face is roughly picked.

Dimensions

Height 42 cm

Width 48 cm

Depth 47 cm

Layout

Three lines of large Greek letters; all are incomplete, but the unjustified left margin suggests a text that was originally centred on the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 58 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Δάμ[ατρικαὶΚόραι]
2. βασιλ[έαῖΙερώνυμον]
3. βασι[λέοςΓέλωνος]
4. [Συρακόσιοι]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1977

Translation (en)

The Syracusans dedicate (this statue of) King Hieronymos, son of King Gelon, to

Damater and Kore

Commentary

The text is speculatively restored in several different ways by previous editors: the text of Manganaro 1977 is provided here as an example; Gentili 1961 instead suggested a dedication to Demeter and Kore by Gelon, son of Hieron. Manganaro is correct that there is theoretically space for a shorter fourth line, and the dedication to Zeus Hellanios in honour of Gelon (ISic3331 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3331>] provides a plausible parallel.

Digital identifiers:

TM 285064

EDR 114431

EDCS 64400280

PHI 331245

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 56.1103.2.2

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0979

Gentili, G.V. 1961. Nuovi elementi di epigrafia siracusana. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 7: 5-25. At 8-10 no.3

Manganaro, G. 1963. Tauromenitana: un calendario romano di Tauromenion. *Arch. Class.* 15: 13-31. At 24

Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 186 no.2 tav.64

Manganaro, G. 1965. Una epistola di Gerone II ai Siracusani (IG XIV.7). *Athenaeum*. 43: 312-320. At 315 n.11

Dimartino, A. 2006. Per una revisione dei documenti epigrafici siracusani pertinenti al regno di Ierone II. In Michelini, C.(eds.), *Guerra e pace in Sicilia e nel Mediterraneo antico (VIII-III sec. a.C.)*. Arte, prassi e teoria della pace e della guerra. Pisa. pp. 703-717. At no.2.2

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3009. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357074>

Photo J. Prag